

Volatile constituents of *Ginkgo biloba* L. leaves from Kumaun : a source of (*E*)-nerolidol and phytol

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Abstract : *Ginkgo* (*Ginkgo biloba* L., Family : Ginkgoaceae), is one of the oldest living tree species; used in traditional medicine to treat blood disorders and potentially keep memory sharp. The essential oils from the leaves of *Ginkgo biloba*, collected from Kumaun region in Uttarakhand, India, was analyzed by capillary GC and GC/MS. Sixty-eight compounds have been identified representing 81.03% of the total oil. The oil was rich in sesquiterpenes (42.11%). Among sesquiterpenes, the major constituents were (*E*)-nerolidol (21.25%), β -bazzanene (6.01%) and (*E*)- γ -bisabolene (2.65%). The other major constituents were phytol isomer (9.4%), α -springene (2.95%), octyl-formate (2.42%), nonanal (2.25%) and diisobutyl phthalate (2.31%) along with *n*-octanol, *cis*-theaspirane, (*E*)- α -ionone, dihydro- β -ionone, (*Z*)-nerolidol ethyl palmitate, *n*-tricosane and geranylgeraniol as minor constituents.

Keywords : *Ginkgo biloba* L., ginkgoaceae, essential oil, (*E*)-nerolidol, Kumaun.

Introduction

Ginkgo biloba L. (Family : Ginkgoaceae) is a deciduous, tough and hardy conifer tree species with separate male and female types and is the oldest living tree species¹. It is also called as living fossil. The plant has short branches with fan like leaves and badly smelled fruits. *Ginkgo* can live as long as 1,000 years and grow up to a height of 120 feet.

Ginkgo is planted for its valuable groups of compounds which have pharmaceutical and medical uses². The plant has been traditionally used for the treatment of various cardiovascular and neurological diseases³. Leave extract has been used in cosmetics and skin care products⁴. In *Ginkgo*, there are two types of biologically active compounds : ginkgoflavonolglycosides and terpenoids⁵. The major phenolic compounds found in *Ginkgo* were protocatechoic, *p*-hydroxybenzoic, vanillic, caffeic, isovanillic, *p*-coumaric and sinapic⁶. Although, *Ginkgo* is the native of China, it is also distributed in Nainital, Dehradun, Almora, Ranikhet and Mussorie at an altitude of 1800-2000 m⁷. Lots of work has been reported on extract composition and biological activity of *Ginkgo* ex-

tract^{3,8-12}. There are some reports on essential oil composition of *G. biloba* from China¹³⁻¹⁵. To the best of our knowledge, this is the first report on essential oil composition of *G. biloba* leaves from India. Therefore, the aim of present study is to analyze essential oil composition of *Ginkgo biloba* leaves.

Results and discussion

The analysis of *Ginkgo biloba* was done by GC and GC/MS analysis. The oil yield of *Ginkgo biloba* was 0.02%. The chemical constituents of the leaves were given in Table 1. Total 68 compounds were identified which represents 81.03% of the total oil. The sesquiterpene was the major class of compounds followed by diterpenes, hydrocarbons, terpene related, esters, aldehydes, alcohols, monoterpenes and other compounds. (*E*)-Nerolidol (21.25%), phytol isomer (9.49%), β -bazzanene (6.01%), α -springene (2.95%), (*E*)- γ -bisabolene (2.65%), *n*-tricosane (2.47%), ethyl palmitate (2.29%), geranylgeraniol (2.24%), octyl-formate (2.42%), nonanal (2.25%) and diisobutyl phthalate (2.31%) were the major constituents of the *Ginkgo* oil along with *n*-octanol

Table 1. Volatile constituents of *Ginkgo biloba* L.

Table-1 (contd.)

Sr. no.	Name of compound ^a	% of oil	RI ^b	RI ^c
1.	α -Pinene (MH)	0.39	935	932
2.	α -Pinene (MH)	0.36	979	974
3.	<i>n</i> -Octanol (alcohol)	1.98	1070	1063
4.	α -Linalool (OM)	0.11	1096	1097
5.	Nonanal (aldehyde)	2.25	1104	1100
6.	β -Terpineol (OM)	0.14	1182	1186
7.	Myrtenol (OM)	0.83	1195	1194
8.	β -Cyclocitral (OM)	0.11	1218	1217
9.	Octyl-formate (ester)	2.42	1264	–
10.	Theaspirane (terpene related)	1.43	1287	–
11.	α -Longipinene (SH)	0.54	1355	1350
12.	α -Ylangene (SH)	0.71	1360	1373
13.	α -Cubebene (SH)	0.79	1383	1387
14.	α -Longifolene (SH)	0.16	1391	1389
15.	α -Caryophyllene (SH)	0.74	1414	1417
16.	(<i>E</i>)- α -Ionone (terpene related)	1.31	1427	1428
17.	Dihydro- β -ionone (terpene related)	1.70	1439	1434
18.	α -Humulene (SH)	0.28	1452	1452
19.	(<i>E</i>)- β -Farnesene (SH)	0.46	1457	1454
20.	β -Camegrene (SH)	0.41	1478	1476
21.	β -Muuroylene (SH)	0.25	1484	1479
22.	As-curcumene (SH)	0.16	1488	1479
23.	(<i>E</i>)- β -Ionone (terpene related)	0.82	1492	1489
24.	α -Ziniberene (SH)	0.70	1499	1493
25.	(<i>E</i>)-(<i>E</i>)- α -Farnesene (SH)	0.41	1508	1505
26.	β-Bazzanene (SH)	6.07	1513	1507
27.	δ -Cadinene (SH)	0.14	1522	1522
28.	(<i>E</i>)-γ-Bisabolene (SH)	2.65	1530	1529
29.	(<i>Z</i>)-Nerolidol (OS)	1.64	1538	1531
30.	(<i>E</i>)- α -Bisabolene (SH)	0.58	1548	1540
31.	(<i>E</i>)-Nerolidol (OS)	21.25	1571	1561
32.	Caryophyllene oxide (OS)	0.05	1584	1582
33.	Fokienol (OS)	0.57	1593	1596
34.	<i>epi</i> -Cubenol (OS)	0.09	1628	1627
35.	γ -Eudesmol (OS)	0.18	1614	1630
36.	<i>epi</i> - α -Muurolol (OS)	0.21	1641	1640
37.	β -Eudesmol (OS)	0.28	1650	1649
38.	α -Cadinol (OS)	0.37	1663	1652
39.	α -Eudesmol (OS)	0.65	1677	1652
40.	α -Bisabolol (OS)	0.16	1684	1685
41.	<i>n</i> -Heptadecane (H)	0.25	1702	1700
42.	Farnesol isomer (OS)	0.33	1714	1714
43.	Drimenol (OS)	0.13	1766	1766
44.	Pentadecanal (aldehyde)	0.34	1773	–
45.	Isopropyl myristate (ester)	0.13	1820	1828

46.	Phytone (DT)	0.55	1830	1830
47.	Diisobutyl phthalate (ester)	2.31	1849	–
48.	<i>n</i> -Nanodecane (H)	0.53	1902	1900
49.	Isophytol (DT)	0.41	1941	1946
50.	α-Springene (DT)	2.95	1972	–
51.	Ethyl palmitate (ester)	1.26	1998	1993
52.	Geranylgeraniol (OS)	1.15	2035	–
53.	Thunbergol (DT)	0.10	2049	–
54.	Abietatriene (DT)	0.27	2061	2055
55.	Cambrene (DT)	0.31	2065	–
56.	<i>n</i> -Henecosane (H)	0.49	2102	2100
57.	Phytol^d isomer (DT)	9.49	2117	–
58.	Cyclopentanone-2,5-(oxohexyl) (ketone)	0.11	2125	–
59.	Linoleic acid (acid)	0.57	2145	2132
60.	<i>n</i> -Tricosane (H)	1.28	2302	2300
61.	<i>n</i> -Docosane (H)	0.39	2202	2200
62.	<i>n</i> -Tetracosane (H)	0.48	2401	2400
63.	<i>n</i> -Pentacosane (H)	0.97	2501	2500
64.	<i>n</i> -Hexacosane (H)	0.49	2600	2600
65.	<i>n</i> -Heptacosane (H)	0.79	2712	2700
66.	<i>n</i> -Octacosane (H)	0.07	2802	2800
67.	Pentatriacortane (H)	0.15	2815	–
68.	<i>l</i> -Hentetracontanol (alcohol)	0.38	2904	–
Total			81.03	
Sesquiterpene			42.11	
Diterpene			14.08	
Hydrocarbon			5.89	
Terpene related			5.26	
Ester			6.12	
Aldehyde			2.59	
Alcohol			2.36	
Monoterpene			1.94	
Acids			0.57	
Ketone			0.11	

^aMode of identification : Retention index, conjunction with standards/ peak enrichment with known oil constituents. ^bRetention indices determined on the Equity-5 column using an *n*-alkane homologous series (C₉–C₃₃). ^cRetention indices from the literature. Bold type indicates major components, *t* = trace (<0.10%); MH-Monoterpene hydrocarbon; OM-Oxygenated monoterpene; H-Hydrocarbon; DT-Diterpene; SH-Sesquiterpene hydrocarbon; OS-Oxygenated sesquiterpene. ^dCorrect isomer (*Z*- or *E*-) not identified with almost same retention index in operating conditions.

(1.98%), *cis*-theaspirane (1.43%), (*E*)- α -ionone (1.31%), dihydro- β -ionone (1.70%), (*Z*)-nerolidol (1.64%), *n*-tricosane (1.28%), ethyl palmitate (1.26%) and geranylgeraniol (1.15%) as minor constituents.

The main constituents identified by Zhang *et al.*¹⁴ were alcohol (17.31%), ketones (13.46%) and aldehydes (11.54%). Monoterpenes and sesquiterpenes represented only, 4.81% of the total oil. The main constituents were palmitic acid (10.79%), myristic acid (7.32%), phytol (3.36%), dodecanoic acid (2.14%), 6-octadecenoic acid (1.77%), farnesylacetone (1.71%), linoleic acid (1.39%), diisobutyl phthalate (1.05%) and geranylacetone (1.00%). Yonghong *et al.*¹³ observed 67 compounds in *Ginkgo* essential oil. The main constituents were hexadecanoic acid (23.48%), cedral (15.19%), 6,10,14-trimethyl-2-pentadecanon (10.89%), butyl 2-methylpropyl ester (9.99%), myristic acid (3.91%), alpha cedrene (2.69%) and nerolidol (1.95%). Our report is entirely different from the previous reports as farnesyl acetone, dodecanoic acid, myristic acid, palmitic acid and 6-octadecanoic acid were totally absent. Our study suggested that *G. biloba* collected from Nainital, was a rich source of (*E*)-nerolidol and phytol. Phytol was found to exhibit antibacterial¹⁶, anticancer, cancer preventive, diuretic and antiinflammatory activity and along with simple sugar/corn syrup used as hardener in candies¹⁷. Nerolidol, a sesquiterpene is known to exhibit antineoplastic¹⁸, antimalarial¹⁹ and antileishmanicidal²⁰ activity and also acts as a skin penetration enhancer for transdermal delivery of therapeutic drugs²¹. It is well documented that both phytol and nerolidol are used in the fragrance industry like cosmetics, shampoos, toilet soaps, household cleaners and detergents^{22,23}. To the best of our knowledge, it is the first report on essential oil composition of *G. biloba* from India.

Experimental

Plant collection and identification :

Ginkgo biloba was collected in the month of June 2013 from Nainital (Uttarakhand, India; N 29°22'58.6'' : E 79°27'34.0'', height 2009 m). The plant was identified by Professor Y. P. S. Pangtey, Botany Department, Kumaun University, Nainital, which has been deposited in the herbarium repository of Botanical Survey of India, Dehradun for future reference (Acc. No. 10359).

Isolation of essential oil :

Fresh leaves of *Ginkgo biloba* (2 kg) were subjected to hydro distillation using a Clevenger apparatus. The

yield of the light yellow coloured essential oil obtained from leaves of *G. biloba* was 0.02% (v/w).

Analysis of the essential oil :

The oil was analysed by using a Shimadzu 2010 auto system GC. The column temperature was programmed at 80 °C (hold time for 2 min) to 210 °C (hold time 5 min) at 3 °C min⁻¹ and than 210–300 °C at 20 °C min⁻¹ with final hold time of 15 min, using N₂/Air at 30.0 mL/min column head pressure as carrier gas, the injector temperature was 270 °C and detector (FID, Flame ionisation detector) temperature 280 °C.

The GC-MS used was Autosystem 2010 GC (Rtx-5, 30 m × 0.25 mm, i.d. 0.25 μm) coupled with Shimadzu QP 2010 plus with thermal desorption system TD 20 with (Rtx-5) fused silica capillary column (30 m × 0.25 mm with film thickness 0.25 μm). The column temperature was 80 °C (hold time for 2 min) to 210 °C (hold time 5 min) at 3 °C min⁻¹ and than 210–300 °C at 20 °C min⁻¹ with final hold time of 21 min, using helium as carrier gas. The injector temperature was 230 °C and 0.2 μL in *n*-hexane, with split ratio of 1 : 30 MS were taken at 70 eV with a mass range of 40–650 amu.

Identification of the components :

Identification of constituents was done on the basis of Retention Indices (RI) relative to *n*-alkanes, indices on a Rtx-5 column and by comparing the fragmentation patterns of mass spectra with the MS Library search (NIST, FFNSC and WILLY) and also comparing with the MS literature data²⁴.

Conclusion

Through GC and GC/MS analysis of leaves oil from *Ginkgo biloba*, it was observed that the plant was rich in (*E*)-nerolidol and phytol. Presence of these compounds made the study important as these compounds are valuable in pharmaceutical industry.

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